

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	6CZUGT36
Principle Investigator	Carina Dargel
Structure/Description	<p>Hydrogenous yeast polar lipid extract from Pichia Pastoris (GS115 HSA): Phosphatidylcholine 63,2% Phosphatidylethanolamine 15,9% Phosphatidylinositol 9,6% Phosphatidylserine 7,25% Cardiolipin 2,3% Phosphatidylglycerol 1,2%</p> <p>Deuterated yeast polar lipid extract from Pichia Pastoris (GS115 HAS): d-Phosphatidylcholine 66,0% d-Phosphatidylethanolamine 14,8% d-Phosphatidylinositol 7,1% d-Phosphatidylserine 6,7% d-Cardiolipin 3,5% d-Phosphatidylglycerol 1,6%</p> <p>Cells grown in shaker flasks at 30°C to late exponential phase (OD~ 20) and lipids extracted/analysed as described in: A. de Ghellinck et al., Production and Analysis of Perdeuterated Lipids from Pichia pastoris Cells, PLoS One, 9 (2014) 9.</p>
Code	Nondeuterated: <i>hPichia Aug 2019 Mid OD 1-5 hpol (63.64%), hPichia Aug 2019 Mid OD 6-7 hpol (36,36%), deuterated: dPichia Aug 2019 dpol 1-2.</i>
Producer	Hanna Wacklin-Knecht/Fatima Plieva
Mass	h-lipids: 613.7 mg (<i>hPichia Aug 2019 63.64% Mid OD 1-5 and 36.36% MID OD 6-7</i>); d-lipids: 214.3mg (<i>dPichia Aug 2019 1-2</i>)
% Deuteration	<i>hPichia Aug2019 MID OD 1-7: 0%; dPichia Aug 2019 1-2; >98%</i>
Analyses	<input type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other <u>_GC-FID_Fame analysis_____</u>

Figure 1. 2D HPLC separation of phospholipid classes for GC analysis. MID1-5/MID 6-7 and d 1-2 were three sets of batches of extractions from h and d *Pichia Pastoris* yeast cultures grown in April-August 2019.

Figure 2. Distribution of fatty acids in hPichia MID1-7 phospholipid extracts separated by TLC into fractions 3–8 from GC-FID analysis of their fatty acid methyl esters (Fame) using GC-FID peak areas. Error bar represents STDEV after two 2D-TLC.

Figure 3. Distribution of fatty acids in dPichia d1-2 phospholipid extracts separated by TLC into fractions 3–8 from GC-FID analysis of their fatty acid methyl esters (Fame) using GC-FID peak areas. Error bar represents STDEV after two 2D-TLC.

Figure 4. Total fatty acid composition of hydrogenous hPichia MID1-7 and deuterated dPichia d 1-2 phospholipid extracts from GC-FID analysis of their fatty acid methyl esters (Fame) using GC-FID peak areas.

Figure 5. Relative phospholipid class composition of hPichia MID1-7 and dPichia d1-2 phospholipid extracts calculated from GC-FID data of fractions 3-8 for.

Table 1. A) Relative phospholipid class composition of total deuterated and non-deuterated yeast phospholipid extracts calculated from GC-FID data. B) Relative composition of fatty acids of different phospholipids for MID 1-5, MID 6-7 and deuterated d 1-2. Error represents STDEV after two 2D-TLC.

A)

Phospholipid:	PC	PE	PI	PS	CL	PG
MID 1-7	63,1±3,3	15,8±2,2	9,5±0,3	7,2±0,6	2,2±0,2	1,2±0,0
d 1-2	66,0±3,7	14,8±2,0	7,1±0,2	6,7±0,4	3,5±0,3	1,6±0,0

B) MID 1-7:

Phospholipid:	PC	PE	PI	PS	CL	PG
C14:0	0,2±0,0	-	-	-	-	-
C16:0	8,9±1,1	23,3±2,3	48,5±2,7	49,2±3,7	9,1±0,5	43,4±0,1
C16:1	7,9±0,3	2,7±0,3	0,1±0,0	0,8±0,1	2,0±0,0	0,1±0,0
C16:2	0,3±0,0	0,1±0,0	0,1±0,0	1,2±0,0	0,1±0,0	0,1±0,0
C17:0	0,3±0,0	-	-	-	-	-
C17:1	1,9±0,1	0,1±0,0	-	0,1±0,0	0,1±0,0	-
C18:0	5,0±0,3	4,8±0,1	6,9±0,6	4,4±0,2	5,9±0,1	9,1±0,3

C18:1	51,7±1,0	44,2±3,6	37,7±5,0	34,0±4,6	48,1±4,8	31,6±1,9
C18:2	16,4±0,3	21,0±1,1	6,7±1,6	10,2±0,4	26,3±2,9	15,8±2,4
C18:3	4,7±0,1	3,8±0,3	0,1±0,0	0,2±0,0	8,7±2,5	0,1±0,0
C20:2	0,3±0,0	-	-	-	-	-

d 1-2:

d-phospholipid:	PC	PE	PI	PS	CL	PG
dC14:0	0,3±0,0	-	-	-	-	-
dC16:0	4,4±0,5	15,2±1,8	45,5±1,2	46,8±3,3	3,1±0,7	38,3±0,1
dC16:1	2,4±0,1	1,0±0,2	1,2±0,1	-	-	-
dC17:0	0,3±0,0	-	0,1±0,0	1,5±0,2	-	-
dC17:1	1,1±0,1	0,1±0,0	-	-	-	-
dC18:0	4,5±0,2	5,3±0,2	11,1±0,4	8,2±0,2	2,1±0,3	-
dC18:1	69,5±1,5	52,3±5,4	38,0±4,1	32,9±4,8	44,0±3,6	27,4±1,7
dC18:2	15,0±0,3	23,5±0,4	4,8±0,8	2,5±0,1	30,7±1,0	4,9±0,8
dC18:3	1,0±0,0	0,3±0,1	-	-	1,5±0,6	0,2±0,1